

A Study on Startup Businesses of Rental Bikes in Bengaluru- “With Special Reference to Bounce and Vogo”

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Abstract

Entrepreneurship is an engine for economic development worldwide. For the developed economies, entrepreneurship is associated with increased productivity and decrease in the unemployment rates, especially among the youth. The developing countries have placed the spotlight on entrepreneurship because of their desperate desire for the economic development and growth. This paper focuses on startups. It has mainly concentrated on two rental bike apps- bounce and vogo. It talks about the growth of these apps and the steps taken by them to fulfill consumer satisfaction to its fullest. It aims at providing convenience to its users. Since transportation plays a major role in our life, bounce and vogo focus on making our lives easier by providing rental bikes at just click of a phone.

Keywords: Innovation, Creativity, Startup and Entrepreneurship

Introduction

The startup scenario in India has gone through a huge makeover, as earlier people were alien to this concept and now that everyone is talking about new innovative businesses. Startups are nothing but a renewed form of doing a business by an entrepreneur. Startups should not be confused with small businesses as the biggest difference is innovation. Recently government of India has launched “Start up India” initiative to foster/support and encourage start up efforts in India. On 15th August 2015, the Prime Minister of India, Shri. Narendra Modi announced the initiative at the Red Fort as Start-up India and on 16th January 2016, it was officially flagged by the then Finance minister Late Shri. Arun Jaitley. In this campaign the main aim of the government is to provide maximum help and support for the new emerging businesses and ideas. The support will be in the form of finance, technology, economic, social as well as environment.

The startups have played a major role in shaping the country’s economy. The success of startups can happen only when the idea is executed in the right way. The Indian government has taken a lot of

steps to ensure that adequate opportunities are being given for young entrepreneurs to implement their ideas. The reason for this happening is because there are countries which are not as well equipped as India but have shown tremendous growth in the economy only because of their appetite for innovation.

According to a report by KPMG, startups have witnessed a seven fold rise in the last ten years. Some startups were founded in the 2000s but since it was a new concept, very few investors were active and the number of organizations supporting startups was limited. In the last ten years, the number of startups has increased and support is also provided on a large scale. Bangalore has now become the startup hub of the country. The report highlights that Bengaluru is the hub of startups in the country as 25 percent of nearly 50,000 startups belong to the city, while second and third in the line are India’s national (Delhi) and financial (Mumbai) capital with 21 percent and 14 percent startups, respectively.[1]

[1][2] <https://www.entrepreneur.com/article/327644>

Thus, this initiative focuses on filling the gap in the economy and its development and has the objective to fire the entrepreneurial blood at the bottom level. It has brought lot of positivity and confidence among the entrepreneurs of India.

According to the NASSCOM-Zinnov startup report titled “Indian Startup Ecosystem Maturing – 2016” currently, India stands at no. three worldwide in terms of largest startup base. This position of India is just after United Kingdom. The report further concludes that, the present efforts and ecosystem is enabling the growth of startups to increase by 2.2 times to reach close to 10,500 startups by 2020.[2]

This research paper provides a critical study of two startup companies. It will furnish a variety of contributions made, the challenges faced and also a comparative study to get a better understanding of startups. It also gives the readers an entire understanding of creating a startup through an idea.

Background

The technology in India has gone through major changes. It has given birth to the concept of rental bikes. Transportation plays a major role in everyone’s life. A proper mode of transport is very important and the rental bike agencies aim to provide this service. Our main focus is to understand the working of these rental bikes and the consumer preferences

The easy access to the internet has made it easier for people to do most of their jobs on their mobile phones. These bike rental apps use a technology called the Internet Of Things which makes it easier for the users to have a problem free booking and also allows them to cancel their rides. The users can also lock or unlock their bikes through the app. Thus, the consumer satisfaction is met.

[2] <https://www.entrepreneur.com/article/327644>

The users are required to create a new account in order to access the app. They have to log in to their account and link their account with their drivers’ license. This thus benefits the users and the owners of the vehicles.

The Bike rental agencies are agencies that provide short term leasing bikes for a specific time and fee. It is mainly organized by the branch offices that are located in different areas. These agencies mainly provide service for people who require temporary transportation within the city or different cities.

Bounce

Bounce (formerly known as Metro bikes) is India’s first two wheeler self-ride rental services.

Bounce is India’s first smart city mobility solution ,with mission of making every day commute street-free, time-saving , reliable and convenient with new one way rental services, users can now

pick up and drop the bike anywhere they need to, and be done with the ride. Bounce was founded in 2014. Headquarters located in Bangalore. Vivekananda Hallekere is the CEO and co-founder of bounce.

Fares starting at Rs. 5/km is the most economical ride around town. Its main motto is anywhere to anywhere. Pick and drop keyless scooters anywhere in the city. Bounce is having 3-4 variants two wheeler where it will be in yellow colour.

Recently the company announced that bounce has reached a significant milestone of 60000 rides per day in Bengaluru, making it the fastest growing bike-sharing start up in the world. Within 10 months of launching dock less scooters in Bengaluru, the firm has completed over five million rides, covering 30 million km.

Vogo

Vogo is India’s first automated scooter rental platform. Now Ola has invested on vogo. Vogo was started in 2016 by Anand Ayyadurai founder and CEO along with Padmanabhan Balakrishnan and Sanchit Mittal. Vogo is a dock less scooter rental company which lets customers rent scooters for short one way trips.

VOGO box is attached to each scooter and lets customers access the key without any human intervention and start riding. They provide Honda active in black colour. The app enables users to locate, unlock and pick-up its scooters and bikes at one point, and drop it off at a different station. Every vogo scooters come with an OTP-based lot sensor. Vogo goal is to make a vogo scooter accessible in every nook and corner of the country which is overwhelmed with issues like traffic congestion, pollution and growing population. Fares charges are 0.1 Rs/min+3 Rs/km on weekdays and 0.1 Rs/min+4 Rs/km on weekends.

Vogo offers rental bike services in Bangalore, Chennai and Hyderabad. They presently offering services in Bangalore and Hyderabad . They allow customers to pick up the vehicle from designated pickup points throughout the city and drop them at any other designated point at the end of the ride. There will a vogo staff at the station to help the clients. The company is trying to tap commuters who are looking for a quick ride for an average distance of about 5-7 kms. It has about 500 scooters in the two cities now. The company said it plans to add over 100 pick up points across both the cities in the coming year.

Comparison between Bounce and Vogo

Bounce	Vogo
Pick from anywhere you find it and drop the bike anywhere	Pick up from vogo zone and drop to nearest vogo zone again
Cheaper if you use for one way rides	Cheaper if you use it for long rides
Bounce is better choice mostly for emergency situations	Better choice if you are using for a day
Availability of helmet is uncertain	Two helmets are given for every ride
There are no staff to assist you about the bike	There is a vogo staff at the station to assist clients
Bounce is costly	Vogo is cheaper
Bounce is having 3-4 variants of scooty in yellow	Vogo is having only Honda active 5G bikes in black
Bounce bikes are maintained well and sometimes tyre is puncture , headlight missings and no fuel in bikes	Vogo bikes are very well maintained and you will always get a proper condition bike with adequate fuel level

Problem Prevailing

Bike rental agencies have taken many steps to provide easy transportation to the consumers, but these facilities are still not used by many consumers due to limitations in time and technology constraints. Thus, this study aims at providing the benefits of such agencies to the users and also a better understanding of the consumer preferences.

Objectives of the Study

- To understand the working of the bike rental agencies.
- To study the purpose of using the bike rental Apps.
- To compare between the two bike rental apps.

Materials and Methods

Sampling technique- Descriptive research

Sample Size - 50 respondents.

Method of sampling – Convenience Sampling

Sources of data - Primary data

Sampling Tool - Questionnaire.

Results

It is found from the study that, out of 50 respondents 46% were male and 54% were female respondents. Thus majority of respondents were female. It can be further seen 4% of the respondents are from the age group below 18 years, 88% of the respondents are from the age group 18-25 years and the least ones are 35 and above which is representing 0%. So we can conclude that the majority of respondents for the survey fall under the age group of 18-25 years. It can be further seen that, 72% of the respondents are students. 24% of the respondents are employees, 2% of the respondents are the business man and 2% are others. Therefore we can conclude that majority of the respondents are students.

Chart Showing the Awareness of Bounce and Vogo Apps

Source: Primary Data

It can be seen that, 94% of the respondents are aware of the bounce and vogo apps and 6% of the respondents are not aware of the bounce and vogo apps. Therefore we can conclude that majority of the respondents are aware of the apps. It can be further seen that, 62% of the respondents are having bike rental app on their phone and 38% of the respondents are not having bike rental app on their phone.

Chart Showing the Presence of Bike Rental Apps on Phone

2. Do you have a bike rental apps on your phone?
50 responses

Source: Primary Data

It can be seen that, 62% of the respondents are having bike rental app on their phone and 38% of the respondents are not having bike rental app on their phone. So we can conclude that majority of them are having the bike rental apps on their phones. It can be further seen that 66% of the respondents have used the bounce and vogo apps and 34% of the respondents have not used the bounce and vogo apps. Therefore we can conclude that majority of the respondents have used the bounce and vogo apps. It can be seen that 20% of the respondents use the bike rental apps regularly and 80% of the respondents use the bike rental apps very rarely. So we can conclude that the majority of the respondents are not using the bike rental apps regularly

Chart Showing the Preference of Bounce and Vogo Apps

5. Which bike rental app do you prefer to use?
50 responses

Source: Primary Data

It can be seen that majority of the respondents prefer to use Bounce and the second highest prefer to use vogo and the least prefer to use other bike rental apps. Therefore we can conclude that majority of the respondents like to use the bounce bike rental app than other apps.

It can be seen that 54% of the respondents use the rental bike apps for personal use, 44% use for both the purpose and 2% use for only professional use. Therefore we can conclude that majority of them use the rental bike app for personal use.

Chart Showing the usage of Bounce and Vogo Apps

7. Why do you use bike rental app?
49 responses

Source: Primary Data

It can be seen that 63.3% of the respondents have told all of above, the second highest 14.3% of the respondents use because it is convenient, 12.2% of the respondents use the rental bike app because it is time saving and 10.2% of the respondents use it because it is cost effective. So we can conclude that the rental bike app is cost effective, time saving and convenient. It can also be noticed that 96% of the respondents recommend to others to use the bike rental apps but 4% of the respondents will not recommend to others to use the bike rental apps. Therefore we can conclude that majority of the respondents will share their experience to others and recommend to use.

Chart Showing the Overall Quality of Bike Rental Apps

9. How would you rate the overall quality of bike rental apps?
50 responses

Source: Primary Data

It can be seen that 60% of the respondents have rated the quality high. 20% of the respondents have rate the quality as the next highest. It can be further seen that a majority of the respondents have rated the overall quality as 4. So we can conclude that they have liked the quality of services.

Discussions

- From the study it can be seen that the female gender are more willing to use bike rental apps falling in the age group of 18-25 are more willing to use the app, who are most the college going students.
- People are aware of such apps and they also have bike rental apps on their phones. But there are many who are hesitant to use the apps.
- The study further shows that 80% of them prefer to use the bounce app over vogo and other apps. Thus the company Vogo and others should work on their customer satisfaction. 96% of the respondents recommend using the bike rental apps and 60% of the respondents rate high grades on the overall quality of the bike rental apps.

Conclusion

The bike rental agencies in India have a huge potential to grow. They are now focusing towards the semi urban and rural areas which are untouched and don't have exposure to such apps. According to our survey, the customers are brand loyal though they are many other bike rental apps. In the survey it is clear that the people are mainly looking for bike rental apps which are convenient, saves times and cost effective.

It is noticeable that the customers are attracted to the bounce app comparatively. Thus other bike rental apps such as Vogo should focus on gaining customers and providing them satisfaction. It can also be seen that the students are majority in number use the bike rental apps. The office goers use such apps occasionally. Thus these bike rental apps should take effective steps to not only grow among the student users but also the others. The apps should work on the promotions and advertising for expansion and growth. Another factor is that the technology should be user friendly and everyone should be able to use it hassle-free. So finally we can say that the quality of service do effect the customers' satisfaction.

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